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Research Article

Synthesis, Physicochemical, Thermal, Electrical and Antibacterial Studies of Transition Metal Chelates of Bistridentate Schiff Base Derived From 2-4 Dyhydroxy 5- Acetyl Acetophenone And 2-Aminothiophenol

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ABSTRACT

The solid complexes of Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II) were prepared from bis tridentate Schiff base ligand derived from 2,4-dihydroxy-5-acetyl acetophenone and 2-aminothiophenol. Analytical IR, ¹H-NMR and mass spectral data of ligand showed its existence predominantly in the intramolecular hydrogen bonded keto imine form. These metal complexes were characterized by elemental analyses-Vis and IR spectroscopy, magnetic measurement, and thermal analysis. The complexes were found to be quite stable and decomposition of the complexes ended with respective metal oxide as a final product. The IR spectral data reveal that the ligand behaves as dibasic tridentate with ONS donor atom sequence towards central metal ion. Thermal behavior of the complex was studied and kinetic parameter were evaluated by Horowitz-Metzger method from the thermal decomposition data. The solid electrical conductivity has been measured in their compressed pellet form and compound showed semiconducting behavior as their conductivity increases with increase in temperature. The ligand and its metal complexes were also been screened for their antibacterial activity against E. coli, P. aeruginosa, S. typhi, S. aureus and B. Subtilis by cup plate method and complexes were shown to possess good antibacterial activity than the free ligand.

INTRODUCTION

The chemistry of transition metal complexes including ordinary complexes, polymers and mixed ligand complexes has been extensively

studied till date for their biological importance as well as a wide range of physicochemical properties [1]. A variety of ligands in complexes has enabled the making of the properties of the metal complexes originating due to ligands. Transition

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metal complexes are a class of compounds which can have properties that are not present in ordinary compounds [2, 3]. However, synthetic route leading to metal complexes with pre-established structures and properties has always remained a challenge for chemists. Schiff bases are often used as ligands in coordination chemistry to form metal complexes [4, 5] owing to their metal binding ability. Schiff base ligands such as N_2O_2 , NNNN and ONO form stable complexes with metal ions due to the close proximity of the donor sites. Numerous transition metal complexes derived from Schiff bases have been studied for the interesting and important properties, such as biological activity, catalytic activity in hydrogenation of olefins, transfer of an amino group, photochromic properties and complexation ability towards some toxic metals [6-8] and in the synthesis of important drugs, such as antibiotic, antiallergic, anticancer and antitumor [9, 10]. The aim of our present study is to synthesize and to introduce the Schiff base which engaged in the complexation by involving Ni (II) Cu (II), and Zn metal ions. The characterization of Schiff base ligand and their complexes have done which prompted us to carry such type of work keeping in view of interesting stereochemical and biological aspects. Thus in this present study synthesis and characterization of Ni (II) Cu (II), and Zn (II) complexes with substituted acetophenone and aminothiophenol are described.

Experimental

All the chemicals used as starting materials for the synthesis of ligand and its metal complexes were of analytical grades and used as received. All the required solvent were purified and dried before use according to the standard method [11].

Synthesis of 2-4 dihydroxy 5-acetyl 2-amino thiophenol (DHAATP) ligands:

A hot ethanolic solution of 2,4-dihydroxy-5-acetyl acetophenone (DHA) (3.88 gm, 0.02 mol) was mixed with an ethanolic solution of 2-aminothiophenol (2.18 am, 0.02 mol) and the reaction mixture was refluxed for about 8 h. The reaction mix was cooled at room temperature and the golden brown coloured product obtained was filtered, washed with ethanol, petroleum ether and dried in vacuo. Yield. 79%, m.p.253 °C

NMR ($CDCl_3 + DMSO$) δ 12.15 (2H, s, phenolic OH), δ 11.10 (2H, s, imino N-H), δ 2.8 (6H, s, methyl), 6.47 and 7.92 ppm (2H, s, Phenyl), δ 3.90 (1H, s, thiophenolic), 7.3 ppm (2h, m, Phenyl), 7.6 And 7.1 ppm (2H, m, phenyl)

Synthesis of Ni (II), Cu (II) and Zn (II) Complexes

The metal complex of Ni (II), Cu (II) and Zn (II) were prepared by following general method. Equimolar quantities (0.01 mol) of metal salts and ligand were dissolved separately in hot ethanol and DMF respectively. These clear solutions were mixed in hot condition with constant stirring. The reaction mixture was refluxed on sand bath for 4-5h. The progress of the reaction was signaled by color change of the resulting solution. The solid products are precipitate, filtered, washed with ethanol and DMF and dried over anhydrous $CaCl_2$ in a desiccator.

Biological Study

The antibacterial activities of the ligand and the complexes have been carried out against the

bacteria *Staphalococcus aureus*, *Bacillus Subtilis*, *Salmonella typhimurium*, *P. aeruginosa* and *Escherichia coli* using nutrient agar medium by the disc diffusion method. Solutions of 100, 200 and 300 ppm of the compounds in DMSO were used for the studies. These discs were placed on the already seeded plates and incubated at 35°C for 24h. The diameter (mm) of the inhibition zone around each disc was measured after 24h.

Physical measurements

The estimation of carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen were obtained on a Carlo-Erba 1108 C-H-N-analyzer at micro analytical unit SAIF, CDRI, Luknow. The IR spectra were recorded in KBr pellets on a Perkin-Elmer-1600 FT-IR spectrophotometer. The reflectance spectra of the complexes were recorded on a Carry-2390 spectrophotometer using BaSO₄ as a dilutant and MgO as a reference in the range 200-1500 nm at SAIF, IIT Chennai. ¹H-NMR spectrum of the ligand was recorded in a mixed solvent (CDCl₃ + DMSO) on a Bruker AC-200F, 300MHz, NMR spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard at RSIC- Punjab university, Chandigarh. Magnetic measurements were carried out at room temperature using Gouy's method using Hg [Co (SCN)₄] as calibrant and values were corrected for diamagnetism by using Pascal's constant. Thermogravimetric analyses of the complexes were carried out using a TGS-2Perkin Elmer thermal analyzer in the temperature range 50-700 °C at a heating rate of 10 °C min⁻¹. Electrical conductivity of the complexes was measured in their compressed pellet form over a range of 313-413 K temperature using Zentech electrometer. Antibacterial and antifungal activities of the ligand and their complexes were carried out against the bacteria, *E. coli*, *S. abony*, *S. aureus*, *P. aeruginosa* and *B. subtilis* by disc diffusion method. SEM

image measurements of complex were recorded at SAIF, Kochi, India.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The reaction of 2,4-dihydroxy-5-acetyl acetophenone and 2-aminothiophenol gives the desired symmetrical tetradentate Schiff base ligand in high yields and purity. The physical characterization and micro analytical data of ligand and its coordination complexes are given in (table 1). All the complexes are coloured solids, air stable and are having line solubility in polar solvents DMF and DMSO. The elemental analysis shown in table 1 indicates that all these complexes have 1:1 metal: ligand stoichiometry.

Electronic spectra and magnetic studies

The electronic spectrum of Ni (II) complex consisted of three bands at 10319, 17543 cm⁻¹ and 24937 cm⁻¹ assignable to the transitions ³A_{2g} → ³T_{2g}, ³A_{2g} (F) → ³T_{2g} and ³A_{2g} → ³T_{1g} (P), respectively corresponds to octahedral geometry around the metal ion [15]. The observed magnetic moment value of Ni (II) complex 2.85 B. M. supported high-spin octahedral geometry for Ni(II) complex. The magnetic moment for Cu (II) complex was found to be 1.86 B.M. at room temperature corresponding to one unpaired electron [15]. The electronic spectrum of Cu (II) complex displayed bands at 17211, 19074 and 20920 cm⁻¹ as signed for the ²B_{1g} → ²A_{1g}, ²B_{1g} → ²B_{2g} and ²B_{1g} → ²E_g transitions, respectively. The electronic transitions and magnetic moment value suggests pseudo octahedral geometry around Cu (II) ion [16, 17]. The Zn (II) complex does not show any d-d bands and are found to be diamagnetic, as expected for d¹⁰ system. On the basis of literature survey, that the Zn (II) complex have tetrahedral geometry [18, 19].

Infrared Spectra

The analysis of IR spectra of DHAATP and its metal complexes are summaries in table 2 which are found to be comparable with each other. The Schiff base ligand exhibit band at 2980cm^{-1} due to the intramolecular hydrogen bonding $\nu(\text{OH})$ group [20]. The absence of this band in the spectra of complexes indicates the deprotonation of the phenolic $\nu(\text{O-H})$ group and coordination of oxygen atom to the metal ion. IR spectra show strong band at 1620cm^{-1} due to $\nu(\text{C=N})$ azomethine mode, which shifted to lower range by $33\text{-}27\text{cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes indicating coordination through azomethine nitrogen to the metal ion. The negative shift may be attributed to the formation of coordinate bond by donation of lone pair of electrons from nitrogen to the metal ion thereby decreasing electron density on nitrogen and it therefore, withdraw electrons from C=N (Pi bond). As a consequence, double bond character decreases and energy required to stretch the bond also decreases. Therefore red shift is occurs. The upward shift of $\nu(\text{C-O})$ (phenolic) band at 1275cm^{-1} of the ligand by $10\text{-}24\text{cm}^{-1}$ and the appearance of new band at $580\text{-}513\text{cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra of all the complexes is observed which further supports the involvement of phenolic oxygen in coordination. The $\nu(\text{S-H})$ stretching vibration of amino thiophenol is not useful since it display very weak band in the ligand and complex spectra. However the participation of the $\nu(\text{S-H})$ group in chelation is ascertained from the shift of the $\nu_{\text{asy}}(\text{C-S})$ and $\nu_{\text{sym}}(\text{C-S})$ from $705\text{-}748\text{cm}^{-1}$ [21] to lower or higher wavelength in the spectra of the complexes. New bands are found in the spectra of the complexes in the region $513\text{-}580\text{cm}^{-1}$ which are assignable to $\nu(\text{M-O})$ stretching vibration for metal complexes. The band at $418\text{-}431\text{cm}^{-1}$ assigned to (M-S) thiophenol [22]. For metal complexes a strong new band is observed at $472\text{-}430\text{cm}^{-1}$ which is attributed to $\nu(\text{M-N})$ vibrations. The IR spectra of all complexes show bands for the presence of water molecules. A broad and strong

band centered in the region $3300\text{-}3500\text{cm}^{-1}$ and another sharp shoulder in the region $1650\text{-}1500\text{cm}^{-1}$ may be assigned to $\nu(\text{OH})$ and of (HOH) vibrations of water molecules respectively [23]. The additional strong band at $878\text{-}820\text{cm}^{-1}$ arising due to $\nu(\text{OH})$ rocking vibration in the spectra of the complexes further confirms the coordinated water molecules.

TGA Analysis

The analysis of thermograms of DHAATP and its metal complexes (fig.1) reveals a two stage decomposition pattern for all the synthesized metal complexes. The ligand DHAATP and the metal complexes of Ni (II), Cu (II), and Zn (II) complexes show no weight loss upto 130°C revealing the absence of lattice water molecule. The TG curve show weight-loss upto 235°C corresponding to loss of two coordinated water molecules in the complexes of Ni (II), Cu (II), and Zn (II) [% wt. loss, obs./calcd.; Ni(II) : 7.24/7.15 ; Cu(II): 7.15/7.09 and Zn(II) : 7.11/7.06 respectively. The thermograms of Ni (II) and Cu (II) show gradual weight loss upto the range 285°C corresponding to the loss of one acetate group [% wt. loss, obs./calcd.; Ni(II) : 5.35/5.08 ; Cu(II): 5.88/5.57 ; In complexes of Ni (II) weight-loss have been observed due to the presence of one methanol group supported by IR spectral data. In all complexes, gradual but continues weight-loss observed beyond 355°C corresponding to the thermal degradation of coordinated ligand molecules. The horizontal curve are obtained in the temperature range $610\text{-}680^{\circ}\text{C}$ indicating the formation of metal oxide. The thermal stability of metal complexes was found to increase periodically with increase in atomic number of the metal and large value of charge/radius ratio [24]. The thermogravimetric analysis has proved to be useful analytical technique in evaluating thermodynamic activation parameters of the

complexes upon thermal decomposition process, such as energy of activation (E_a), frequency factor (Z) and entropy change ($-\Delta S$) by employing Coats-Redfern method [25] and values obtained are given in table.3. The half decomposition temperature of the compounds decreases in the order:

DHAATP > Ni (II) > Cu (II) > Zn (II)

Electrical conductivity

The temperature dependence of electrical conductivity of DHAATP and its complexes reveals a linear trends fig. 2 and data is cited in table 1 from the result it is observed that the electrical conductivity of DHAATP and its complexes show a tendency to increase by raising the temperature up to 403K. The electrical conductivity of these complexes lies in the range 2.17×10^{-8} to $4.60 \times 10^{-10} \Omega^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$ at 373K. The activation energy of electrical conduction of the complexes is found to be in the range 0.280 to 0.610 eV. The order of electrical conductivity of HMACHZ and their complexes at 373K is found to be Zn (II) > Cu (II) > Ni (II).

Biological study

The ligand DHAATP and its complexes are found to show inhibitory activity against all the gram positive and gram negative bacterial strains (fig. 3 and table 4). The complexes of Ni (II), Zn (II) and ligand DHAATP show moderate antibacterial activity. The Cu (II) show maximum inhibitory activity against *S. aureus*. Ni (II) show maximum activity against the *S. typhi* (gram positive bacteria), Ni(II) and Zn(II) show moderate antibacterial activity against *S. Typhi*. All the metal complexes show moderate antibacterial activity against the *P. Aeruginosa* (gram negative bacteria) and *B. Subtilis* (gram positive bacterial strain). It can be concluded that the ligand

DHAATP and its complexes are bioactive against all the bacterial strains. The increase or decrease of antimicrobial activity of ligands upon coordination may be due to structural change in functional group responsible for antimicrobial action. The antimicrobial effect varies with metal ion as well as organism. Similar correlation and increase in antibacterial activity of ligands on complexation with reference to parent ligands has been well cited. Such increased activity of the metal chelates can be explained on the basis of overtone concept and Tweedy Chelation, theory [26]. According to overtone concept of cell permeability, the lipid membrane that surrounds the cell favors the passage of only lipid soluble materials due to which liposolubility is an important factor that controls antimicrobial activity. On chelation the polarity of metal ion is reduced to a greater extent due to the overlap of the ligand. Orbital and partial sharing of the positive charge of the metal ion with donar group. Further, it increases the delocalization of π electrons over the whole chelates ring and enhances lipophilicity of the complex. The increased lipophilicity of complexes permit easy penetration into lipid membranes of organisms and facilitates as blockage of metal binding site in enzymes.

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Figure 1: Thermogram of DHAATP and its complexes

Fig 2: Temperature dependence of log σ

Fig. 3: Zone of inhibitions of ligand DHAATP and its complexes

Table 1: The Proposed Composition, Formula weight Color, Time of Reflux and Elemental analysis of DHAATP Complexes

S.N.	Proposed composition of the complexes	χ ($\square^{\square} \text{cm}^{-1} \square$)	Ea (eV)	Color	M%	C%	H%	N%
1	[Ni(L)2H ₂ O(OAc)]	4.55 x10 ⁻⁹	0.591	Waking earth	11.45 (11.66)	52.34 (52.51)	4.00 (4.010)	5.44 (5.57)
2	[Cu(L)2H ₂ O(OAc)]	2.17 x10 ⁻⁸	0.309	Bottle olives	12.23 (12.49)	51.90 (52.01)	3.56 (3.97)	5.10 (5.51)
3	[Zn(L)2H ₂ O(OH)]	4.16x10 ⁻¹⁰	0.520	Kesar milk	12.56 (12.82)	50.78 (51.82)	3.45 (3.95)	5.23 (5.49)

Table 2: IR Spectral data (cm⁻¹) of the Ligand (DHAATP) and metal complexes

S. N.	Ligand/Complexes	ν (O-H)	ν (S-H)	ν (C=N)	ν (C-O)	ν (M-O)	ν (M-N)	ν (M-S)	ν (H ₂ O)
1	DHAATP	2910	2540	1620	1275	--	--	--	--
2	[Ni(L)2H ₂ O(OAc)]	--	2590	1589	1294	580	435	418	3389,878,1633
3	[Cu(L)2H ₂ O(OAc)]	--	2590	1593	1295	513	458	429	3377,868,1641
4	[Zn(L)2H ₂ O(OH)]	--	2510	1589	1287	550	432	426	3390,872,1639

Table 3: Thermal decomposition data of DHAATP and its complexes.

S.N.	Compound	Half Decomposition Temp. °C	Activation Energy Ea(kJ mole ⁻¹)	Frequency Factor (Z) (Sec ⁻¹)	Entropy Change ΔS(KJ mole ⁻¹)	Free Energy Change Δ G(KJ mole ⁻¹)
1	DHAATP	480	31.22	3.76x10 ⁻⁷	235.067	-112752
5	[Ni(L)2H ₂ O(OAc)]	430	59.34	4.49x10 ⁻¹⁰	360.048	-154771
6	[Cu(L)2H ₂ O(OAc)]	425	74.07	5.81x10 ⁻⁹	318.696	-135385
7	[Zn(L)2H ₂ O(OH)]	390	34.47	1.98x10 ⁻⁶	162.955	-63475

Table 4: Zone of inhibition of growth of Microorganism

S.N.	Schiff base /complexes	Gram-positive bacteria			Gram-negative bacteria	
		<i>E. Coli</i> (mm)	<i>P. Aeruginosa</i> (mm)	<i>S. Typhi</i> (mm)	<i>S. Aureus</i> (mm)	<i>B. Subtilis</i> (mm)
5	Ni. DHAATP	14	10	14	16	11
6	Cu. DHAATP	16	14	12	17	12
7	Zn. DHAATP	11	13	14	15	10

* Weak measurable inhibitory action; 0-9; 9 – 15: moderate and 15 and above: significant.